

ANZO

Zosterops lateralis

Southern Melanesia

Bootstrap

- Chatham Island
- New Zealand - South Island
- Western and South Australia
- Tasmania,
New South Wales,
Victoria
- French Polynesia
- New Zealand - North Island
- Norfolk Island
- Heron Island
- Queensland
- Lord Howe Island
- Pentecost
- Ambrym
- Ambae
- Malekula
- Gaua
- Vanua Lava
- Espiritu Santo
- Tanna
- Efate
- Lifou
- Ouvea
- Grand Terre
- Mare
- Zosterops xanthochrous
- Zosterops minutus
- Zosterops inornatus
- Zosterops tenuirostris
- Zosterops flavifrons
- Zosterops tenuirostris
- Zosterops borbonicus